

D6.2

1st annual report on communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities

VO.3

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ABBREVIATIONS

C, D & E: Communication, dissemination, and exploitation

HEU: Horizon Europe

KER: Key Exploitable Result

MCO: EHPA Manufacturers Committee

PUSH2HEAT: Pushing forward the market potential and business models of waste heat valorisation by full-scale demonstration of next-gen heat upgrade technologies in various industrial contexts.

R&I Committee: EHPA Research and Innovation Committee

WPs: Work Package (s)

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PARTNERS

TEC: Fundacion Tecnalia Research & Innovation

TECV: Tecnalia Ventures (Affiliated of TEC)

UPV: Universitat Politècnica de València

BSNOVA: BS Nova Apparatebau GmbH

SPH: SPH Sustainable Process Heat GmbH

VITO: Flemish Institute for Technological Research

FH: Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Foederung der Angewandten Forschung E.V

POLIMI: Politecnico di Milano

QPINCH: Qpinch NV

ENER: Enertime SA

ENCI: Enegy Circulaire (Affiliated of ENER)

TUB: Technische Universität Berlin

STC: Schoeller Technocell GmbH & Co KG

CARTIF: Fundación Cartif

OST: Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences (Associated Partner)

BONO: Bono Energia S.P.A

CDG: Cartiere di Guarcino S.P.A

DYNASOL: Dynasol Group

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LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: PUSH2HEAT logo.....	9
Figure 2: Brand design guide stills	10
Figure 3: PUSH2HEAT Powerpoint template.....	11
Figure 4: PUSH2HEAT report template.....	11
Figure 5: PUSH2HEAT minute taking template	12
Figure 6: PUSH2HEAT flyer	13
Figure 7: PUSH2HEAT A4 poster	13
Figure 8: PUSH2HEAT website.....	14
Figure 9: PUSH2HEAT newsletter template.....	16
Figure 10: PUSH2HEAT Newsletter registration form.....	17
Figure 11: stills from promotional video.....	18
Figure 12: Visual for Online Seminar	25
Figure 13. Application of Horizon Results Booster in PUSH2HEAT	28
Figure 14. Form used during the working session to reflect on KER's definition	28
Figure 15. Template in 4 slides for the first identification of KER.....	29
Figure 16. Template for the definition of KER, version 2	29

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: PUSH2HEAT events.....	19
Table 2. List of Key Exploitable Results (KER).....	29

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	7
2. OBJECTIVES	8
3. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE 1ST YEAR	9
3.1 Visual identity	9
3.1.1 Dissemination templates.....	10
3.1.2 Project promotional materials and Communication toolkit	12
3.2 Website	14
3.3 Social media Channels	15
3.4 E-Newsletter	16
3.4.1 Stakeholder Network	17
3.5 Promotional video	18
3.6 Project Media and press releases	18
4. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE 1ST YEAR	19
4.1 Participation in conferences and events	19
4.1.1 Collaboration with EU Projects	24
4.2 Scientific publications	26
5. EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE 1ST YEAR	27
5.1 1st Workshop on exploitation	27
6. CONCLUSION	30

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1. INTRODUCTION

One of the European Commission's four main priorities as part of the new strategic agenda for the EU 2019-2024 is building a climate-neutral, green, fair, and social Europe, identifying "accelerating the transition to renewables and increasing energy efficiency" among the priority actions. Along the same line, the European Green Deal aims to build a carbon-neutral Europe by 2050.

Considering the weight that industrial process heat has in the total energy demand of the European industry, the first step towards decarbonization in the industrial sector is increasing energy efficiency through the recovery and upgrade of waste heat.

Despite the existence of heat pump technologies for heat upgrading, their wide deployment is not taking place due to various technical and non-technical barriers hindering the uptake. In this context, PUSH2HEAT will work towards overcoming these implementation barriers and push forward the market potential and business models of heat upgrade technologies by the full-scale demonstration of diverse heat upgrading heat pumps in relevant industrial sectors with high waste heat recovery and upgrading potential, as well as with a supply temperature range of 90–160°C.

This deliverable (D6.2) intends to collect and present all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities carried out during the first 12 months of the project. This way spotlighting all the efforts dedicated to raising awareness, promoting the PUSH2HEAT project and its related results, and knowledge generated within and beyond the project, as described in D6.1, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy.

This is the first of four reports that will be also prepared on M24, M36, M48.

2. OBJECTIVES

The annual report on communication, dissemination and exploitation aims to provide a clear overview of how all the communication channels and activities have worked together to address the initially identified stakeholder groups, as indicated in deliverable 6.1.

EHPA, as the Work Package leader of PUSH2HEAT's WP6 (Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation of Project results), has overseen coordinating the implementation of the Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities with the cooperation, direct involvement, and support of the other Work Package leaders and all the project partners,

As described in D6.1, the approach to communication and dissemination is different depending on the phase of its development. The activities gathered in this deliverable follow the approach of **Phase I**.

Phase I: Raise interest among key stakeholders aims at establishing a common project identity and raise awareness and interest regarding the project's expected results and impacts.

This report will be divided into three areas:

- **Communication activities:** focusing on the promotion of the project's activities and raising awareness of the benefits of heat upgrading technologies to a general audience, including decision-makers.
- **Dissemination activities:** focusing on the spread of the technical results of PUSH2HEAT to identified target groups and fostering collaborations with other related projects.
- **Exploitation activities:** focusing on ensuring the life-beyond-the-project of the PUSH2HEAT's Generated results.

3. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE 1ST YEAR

An essential aspect of the project's strategy is its communication plan, which aims to disseminate the project's vision to a broader community of stakeholders. Throughout the first year, the communication activities within the project have focused on raising interest among key stakeholders, extending beyond the project's internal communities to engage with wider quadruple helix audience (public authorities, industry representatives, academia and citizens).

In line with the project's communication objectives, a series of communication channels were chosen to ensure an effective engagement and awareness of the challenges, technical advancements, and economic benefits associated with heat upgrading technologies.

3.1 Visual identity

A common branding was created by EHPA and approved by all consortium partners in M4 to ensure the immediate recognition of the project. This common branding includes the official PUSH2HEAT logo (Figure 1) and it has been applied to dissemination templates for Microsoft Word and Microsoft PowerPoint to be used for presentations and reporting and a poster and a brochure, part of the communication toolkit.

Figure 1: PUSH2HEAT logo

Figure 2: Brand design guide stills

3.1.1 Dissemination templates

A series of dissemination templates for Microsoft Word and Microsoft PowerPoint were developed by EHPA following any applicable rules and regulations of the European Commission and are currently being used by all partners for project presentations, reporting and minute taking. *Insert Figures (add in the annex pwp presentation and word document)*

Figure 3: PUSH2HEAT Powerpoint template

Figure 4: PUSH2HEAT report template

Figure 5: PUSH2HEAT minute taking template

3.1.2 Project promotional materials and Communication toolkit

Using the branding, a brochure and A4 poster were developed. These promotional materials aim to raise awareness and provide visibility among the large non-specialist community and our audience of stakeholders and have already been used in public events. Printouts are being kept to a minimum for environmental reasons.

Figure 6: PUSH2HEAT flyer

Figure 7: PUSH2HEAT A4 poster

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A second version of the promotional toolkit, oriented towards disseminating initial project results should be elaborated by M24.

3.2 Website

The [PUSH2HEAT website](#) was developed by EHPA in the early stages of the project, based on the branding. The website acts as a hub to collect all PUSH2HEAT related public information, allowing stakeholders and others to access at any time the projects' aims, development, deliverables, newsletters, webinars, and preliminary results.

The website is maintained and updated by EHPA; however, all partners must be involved in developing content to provide the visibility of the project and maximize its impact. Due to its nature serving as the main communication and dissemination platform, the website will be constantly updated and improved to suit the project's needs, during the project lifecycle and up to two years after its completion.

It is directly connected to the project's social media channels ([LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#) and [Youtube](#)) to ensure a wider dissemination to a technical and non-technical audience; it is also linked to all consortium partners websites.

Figure 8: PUSH2HEAT website

3.3 Social media Channels

[Twitter](#) and mainly [LinkedIn](#) were established as the primary social media channels for disseminating the work of PUSH2HEAT due to their effectiveness in reaching our target stakeholder groups. Twitter enables us to share concise and timely updates, while LinkedIn allows for more in-depth content sharing.

The social media accounts have been consistently used to share posts related to project updates, news, relevant events and other topics of relevance, with these channels we aim to maintain an active online presence, keep stakeholders informed and engage in discussions regarding the project's themes.

Based on our observations during the first year of the project, it has been evident that PUSH2HEAT experiences significantly higher engagement on LinkedIn compared to Twitter, our primary social media platforms. We have observed a noteworthy increase in visitor traffic, post impressions, and post engagements on LinkedIn. Since the initiation of the project, our LinkedIn following has grown by 310 followers, whereas our Twitter following has only seen a modest growth of 30 followers. Furthermore, our current audience and valued partners exhibit greater levels of interaction and engagement on LinkedIn as opposed to Twitter.

A dedicated [YouTube](#) channel has been established to serve as a centralized repository for all PUSH2HEAT video content produced throughout the project's duration. This includes a wide range of videos such as online seminars, promotional videos, and other relevant audio-visual materials. The YouTube channel has been created to ensure convenient access and easy dissemination of these valuable resources to project stakeholders, partners, and the wider audience interested in the project's activities and outcomes.

To foster collaborative engagement and maximize the reach of our project's outcomes, we actively encourage consortium partners to contribute to the content that is to be published across our social media channels as well as to reshare the posts that they find relevant to their audience. By providing their valuable insights and resources, our partners can play a vital role in generating compelling content. Additionally, we encourage our partners to tag the project in their related posts on their own social media accounts. This collaborative effort not only enhances our project's visibility but also aids in building a broader audience and facilitates the dissemination of our results to a wider community.

3.4 E-Newsletter

The PUSH2HEAT newsletter was created to provide updated information about the project to relevant key stakeholders. The first edition was sent electronically in April 2023.

The first edition of the project's bi-annual newsletter was sent in April 2023 to the PUSH2HEAT Stakeholder Network that had at the time of sending, 276 members, including Consortium partners.

Figure 9: PUSH2HEAT newsletter template

6 other Newsletters are planned throughout the project, with the suggested scheduled below:

- October 2023
- April 2024
- October 2024
- April 2025
- October 2025

- April 2026

3.4.1 Stakeholder Network

The stakeholder Network is an evolving community that has been progressively developed throughout the first months of the project. Its purpose is to bring together stakeholders who have expressed interest in staying informed about PUSH2HEAT's activities. The initial list was formed by leveraging the contacts within the Project Consortium partner networks, with individuals who had shown interest in receiving updates about the project. Additional members were added to the network through two main channels:

- The [registration form](#) available on the PUSH2HEAT website, which was promoted through the project's social media accounts.

Figure 10: PUSH2HEAT Newsletter registration form

- The participation in the first PUSH2HEAT webinar, during which attendees had the opportunity to indicate their interest in joining the Stakeholder Network.

3.5 Promotional video

A promotional animation video was developed to share the project's purpose and goals with a wider audience. The aim was to raise awareness and generate interest in the PUSH2Heat project. The video will be made available in the coming weeks.

Figure 11: stills from promotional video.

3.6 Project Media and press releases

- **November 2022:**
 - o EHPA published a press release to celebrate the project kick-off. Available [here](#).
 - o Enertime issued a press release regarding their participation in the PUSH2HEAT project. Available [here](#).
- **August 2023:**
 - o Tecnalia released an article about the PUSH2HEAT project, which was published by [InnovaSpain](#) and [ESEficiencia.es](#)

4. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE 1ST YEAR

4.1 Participation in conferences and events

To boost the consortium's visibility, PUSH2HEAT, and its progress, have been presented in several EU and international forums and events related to the scope of the project.

Table 1: PUSH2HEAT events

Partner	Event	Date	Location	Type of participation	Photo
EHPA	Chillventa 2022	11-13 October 2022	Nuremberg, Germany	Booth and flyer dissemination	
ENERTIME	SET Plan Conference	9-10 November 2022	Prague, Czechia	Booth and flyer dissemination	

SPH	Deutsche Kälte und Klimatagung	18 November 2022	Magdeburg, Germany	Presentation	
SPH	CEPI - EHPA event: Heat Pumps and paper industry	2 February 2023	Brussels, Belgium	Presentation and flyer dissemination	
TECNALIA	Internal workshop in ASPAPEL (Spanish Association of Pulp, Paper and Cardboard)	10 February 2023	Spain	Presentation	
TECNALIA	Internal workshop for PepsiCo	21 February 2023	Online	Presentation	

	company. "Pathways towards decarbonisation of industrial processes."				
TECNALIA	GENERA Fair	23 February 2023	Madrid, Spain	Presentation: "The High Temperature Heat Pump: technology for the decarbonization of thermal demand through the recovery of low-temperature residual heat"	
EHPA	Research and Innovation Committee EHPA	9 March 2023	Online	Presentation	
EHPA	ISH Frankfurt	13-15 March 2023	Frankfurt, Germany	Booth and flyer dissemination	
ENCI	Global CemProducer Conference & Exhibition	14-15 March 2023	Munich, Germany	Presentation	

TECNALIA	EL PERTE de descarbonización industrial y las ayudas CDTI.	19 April 2023	Madrid, Spain	Presentation: "BCs y AHTs para la recuperación y upgrade de calor residual"	
SPH, OST, POLIMI	IEA Heat Pump Conference 2023	15-18 May 2023	Chicago, USA	Presentation and flyer dissemination	
TECNALIA	Food4Future Fair & Conference. food industry"	16 May 2023	Bilbao, Spain	Presentation: "Pathways towards decarbonisation of thermal processes in the"	
VITO	Dialogue Meeting "More energy savings? Yes, we can!"	17 May 2023	Online	Presentation	
SPH	NEFI Technology Talk: Steam generation with heat	31 May 2023	Online	Presentation	

	pumps in industry				
EHPA	EUSEW – European Sustainable Energy Week	20-22 June 2023	Brussels, Belgium	Booth and flyer dissemination	
OST	ECOS2023 – International Conference on Efficiency, Cost, Simulation and Environmental Impact of Energy Systems	25-30 June 2023	Gran Canaria, Spain	Presentation	
TUB, OST	International Congress of Refrigeration	21-26 August 2023	Paris, France	Participation + informal discussions about the project	
EHPA, ENCI, ENER	7th International Seminar on ORC Power	4-6 September 2023	Seville, Spain	Presentation	

	Systems (ORC2023)				
EHPA	Heat Pump Forum	27-28 September 2023	Brussels, Belgium	Booth and flyer dissemination	

4.1.1 Collaboration with EU Projects

09/03/2023 – Online participation and discussion with [W4RES](#) project

On the 9th of March of 2023, EHPA hosted the 12th Edition of its Research and Innovation Committee. The R&I Committee includes over 120 members, who meet quarterly to discuss about open project calls and initiatives, among other matters.

In this occasion, the main presentations and discussion was linked to the projects PUSH2HEAT and W4RES (Women for market uptake of renewable heating and cooling). Minutes of the event are available [here](#).

04/04/2023 – Online Seminar with the [SPIRIT](#) project

Figure 12: Visual for Online Seminar

On the 4th of April of 2023 EHPA organized an online seminar called "High-temperature heat pumps: heading towards the decarbonization of industry".

The event served as an opportunity to present the sister projects, SPIRIT and PUSH2HEAT, both aiming to address and overcome the barriers to industrial heat pump growth while exploring their use in the chemical, paper, and food and beverage industries. The webinar, in which the benefits of increasing industrial heat pump were discussed from a project and business perspectives, was attended by over 224 participants.

The recording of the webinar is available [here](#).
The slides of the presentation are available [here](#).

As of August 2023, the video recording has had over 1000 visualizations.

4.2 Scientific publications

- Álvarez, L., Gutiérrez Peinador, V., Linares Corell, B., Iriarte Madurga, E., Bobes Miranda, R. A., Cruzate, J., ... Pérez, L. R. (2023). Análisis energético (Cuadernos). Club Español de la Energía, Deloitte, Garrigues. Retrieved from: https://www.enerclub.es/frontNotebookAction/Biblioteca_/Publicaciones_Enerclub/Cuadernos/CE_72
- Arpagaus, C., Paranjape, S., Nertinger, S., Tietz, R., Bertsch, S.: [Review of Business Models for Industrial Heat Pumps](#), 36th International Conference on Efficiency, Cost, Optimization, Simulation and Environmental Impact of Energy Systems (ECOS 2023), 25-30 June 2023, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain, <https://doi.org/10.52202/069564-0068>

5. EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE 1ST YEAR

5.1 1st Workshop on exploitation

This activity was held the 27th of April of 2023 during the 2nd PUSH2HEAT Consortium meeting in Antwerpen. This workshop is the first of three to be held along the project life aiming at a progressive definition of exploitation potentials, business cases and market opportunities ensuring a growing level of insight on these plans.

The objectives of this first workshop were:

- Create a common understanding among the partners on the purpose of the different exploitation strategies and typologies of results in PUSH2HEAT.
- Discuss the potential for exploitability of results: problem solved and its impact, exploitation mode and preconditions for exploitation.
- Outcomes of the discussions: challenges to be solved and suggestions for the exploitation strategy.

As stated in one of these objectives, it is very important to generate awareness among project partners about the need of exploitation of results being even an obligation in an EU funded project and an opportunity to further scale-up the results. It was stressed the importance of this topic, The final objective should be the generation of an impact (on society, market) which depends on the exploitation strategy and its implementation.

It was also presented the possibility of taking advantage of the EC initiative "Horizon Results Booster" in which EC supports, free of charge, research and innovation projects in dissemination and exploitation through a set of free of charge services lead by experts. A set of 3 tailor-made support services for beneficiaries is offered:

- SERVICE 1: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy in three different modules.
- SERVICE 2: Business Plan Development (BPD).
- SERVICE 3: Go To Market.

These services are deployed through workshops and meetings for guiding, supporting, training and reviewing the work done in the project on these three aspects. Figure 13 shows a possible application of these services along PUSH2HEAT life.

Figure 13. Application of Horizon Results Booster in PUSH2HEAT

A first list of PUSH2HEAT Key Exploitable Results was presented in the workshop, which was consolidated from partners' previous work on this subject describing their expectations on exploitation (see section 5.2 of this document for further details on KER definition). During the workshop, project partners had the opportunity to reflect on aspects like the problem solved with their KER, impact, main exploitation mode, preconditions for exploitation and the collaboration needed from other partners.

14

5.2 Key Exploitable Results identification

Exploitation specifically in PUSH2HEAT has the following characteristics:

- Push2Heat is an Innovation Action → More intense exploitation activity.
- Key Exploitable Result (KER) is a result with commercial or social significance providing knowledge or economic profit to a company.
- KER can be innovative or not.
- KER are not limited to complete systems and prototypes (also component, procedure, model, knowledge, skills...).

- KER. Two approaches: a) individual b) joint exploitation with other project partners.
- For each KER a lead partner is identified, who will be leading the updating of the identification and assessment with regards to that result.

Figure 15.1 Figure 15. Template in 4 slides for the first identification of KER

As a result of this work, PUSH2HEAT project presents a first consolidated list of its key exploitable results, which can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. List of Key Exploitable Results (KER)

Title	Lead partner
Optimized AHT design and AHT control SW	TECNALIA
Dynamic model of Heat Upgrade Technologies applied to industries	UPV
Policy Recommendations	EHPA
Cost Reduction through modularization	SPH
Software heat exchanger design and optimisation	VITO
Implementation of Heat Upgrade Systems and assessment on their commissioning	FRAUNHOFER
Max QCOP	QPINCH
Large Scale High-Temperature Heat Pump with Centrifugal compressor	ENER
High-Temperature Heat Pump with Centrifugal compressor	ENCI
Process and control design of AHT	TUB
Business Models and Contractual Agreements (R12)	OST

After the workshop, an internal review of these KER was made in order to have a more consistent version, aiming always at a common understanding of each question, clarifying the innovation status of the KER or correcting, extending or completing descriptions where needed.

Figure 16. Template for the definition of KER, version 2

6. CONCLUSION

This is the first report on communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. We will produce additional reports at the end of every year of the project, specifically at M24, M36, and M48. In this report, we have outlined the activities conducted during the first year of the project. The upcoming reports will focus on the development of the Push2Heat project activities and brand throughout the project.

